

carried out by comparison with authentic sterol acetate of the R_f on argentation tlc and relative retention time on glc.

Glc was performed on OV-17 on SCOT glass capillary column (30 m × 0.3 mm i.d.) at 255°, injection at 275° and nitrogen carrier gas at 0.60 ml/min (split ratio ca. 100 : 1). RRT in glc was given relative to cholesteryl acetate. The other techniques used in the present work have been described previously⁸. The sterol acetates were shown to contain five phytosterols. The approximate content of each sterol in the acetylated total sterol fraction as determined by glc was : 24 β -methylcholesta-5,22-dien-3 β -ol acetate (brassicasterol, 12.3%) ; (24 ξ)-24-methylcholest-5-en-3 β -ol acetate (campesterol, 5.2%) ; (22E, 24 ξ)-24-ethylcholesta-5,22-dien-3 β -ol acetate (stigmasterol, 36.9%) ; (24 ξ)-24-ethylcholest-5-en-3 β -ol acetate (β -sitosterol, 29.9%) ; and 24-ethylcholest-5,24-dien-3 β -ol (15.7%) of RRT 1.96.

Discussion

It is known that three phytosterols (β -sitosterol, campesterol and stigmasterol) form the major components of sterols in many plants⁴⁻⁶. The number of sterols found in *Salsola foetida* is five, which include relatively large amounts of 24-ethylcholesta-5,24-dienol (15.7% of the total sterol) and brassicasterol (12.3%). The former sterol was first identified in *Withania somnifera*⁶ and the later in *Solanaceous* seeds⁷. It was recently reported⁸ to form biosynthetic intermediate for $\Delta^{2,4(8)}$ -sterol to 24-alkylated sterol conversion.

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Chemical Investigation of *Lonicera maacki*

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THE present investigation on the leaves of *Lonicera maacki* (Caprifoliaceae) resulted in the isolation and characterisation of three known compounds. In addition, the presence of three more biflavones have been indicated by tlc examination of methylated products.

Air dried and powdered leaves (1 kg) of *Lonicera maacki* was Soxhleted with petroleum ether, benzene and chloroform successively for 3 h each. The residue after treatment with petroleum ether and benzene was chromatographed over silica gel using benzene : pyridine : formic acid (36 : 9 : 5) as solvent¹ for separation. Tlc revealed the presence of six bands.

The first compound (80 mg), R_f 0.18, m.p. 322°, was characterised as I-4', II-4', I-5, II-5, I-7, II-7 hexahydroxy (I-3', II-8) biflavone (amentoflavone). On methylation with dimethyl sulphate and anhydrous potassium carbonate in dry acetone it gave colourless crystals of hexa-O-methyl amentoflavone, m.p. 181-82°, (CHCl₃ - MeOH) R_f 0.40. Acetylation (Ac₂O/pyridine) of the compound yielded amentoflavone hexaacetate and crystallisation from CHCl₃ - MeOH gave colourless needles, m.p. 242-43°. The identity was confirmed by the comparison of ¹H-nmr spectra of the derivatives (methylether and acetate) with those of the authentic samples².

The second compound, m.p. 349° (MeOH) was identified as 5,7,4'-trihydroxy flavone and on methylation with dimethyl sulphate gave a trimethyl ether, m.p. 155°. It was characterised as apigenin by chromatographic and spectral comparison with an authentic sample³.

The third flavanone, m.p. 228° gave an intense pink colour with Zn/HCl. Its identity with naringenin was established by direct comparison of the acetate and methyl ether with those of the authentic sample⁴.

Tlc examination of the methylated product of the other three bands showed them to be identical with amentoflavone hexamethyl ether both in R_f value and colour. Tlc of the parent compounds indicated them to be mono-, di- and tri-O-methyl amentoflavone.

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